

1 **An F-box protein that controls tumor size.**

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7 Traditional approaches to identification of factors that regulate cancer cell survival or tumor growth have
8 focused on study of animal models of cancer for in vivo and cell culture models for in vitro discovery. We
9 describe here identification of Fbx15 as a regulator of tumor size in humans with cancer *in vivo* by
10 measuring total transcription in the primary tumor and comparing tumor transcriptome based on diameter
11 of the solid tumor. Fbx15 functioned in concert with the iron sensing system and iron-based cytosolic
12 iron-sulfur (Fe-S) assembly complex consisting of IREB2 and CIAO1/2B. The primary mechanism by
13 which Fbx15 exerted its size-regulating function was through control of CRL ligase complex composition in
14 the tumor through regulation of cullin CUL1, RBX1 and SKP1 together with a second F-box protein,
15 Fbx14.
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